

A Thematic Analysis Of The Oscar Winning Documentary: The Elephant Whisperers

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Abstract :

The Elephant Whispers Documentary is a short documentary released on Netflix in 2022 directed by Kartiki Gonsalves and produced by Sikh Entertainment. It is a short documentary made in Tamil language and later dubbed in many languages. It is the first documentary to win the Academy Award for Best Documentary Short Film at the 95th Academy Awards. This documentary depicts the life of a couple named Boman and Bailey, who are entrusted with the care of an orphaned baby elephant named Raghu. Many elephant cubs died due to lack of proper care, so Raghu was handed over to them. Both of them faced many difficulties in taking care of Raghu and raising him properly and with time Raghu grew up. And a familial bond is established between Raghu and the couple and they start treating Raghu as their own child and considering Raghu's good upbringing, they are adopted by the forest department as another baby elephant named Ammukutty. They finally take Raghu back. This documentary is depicted in the Mudumalai National Park bordering the Indian states of Karnataka and Tamil Nadu. The documentary showcases the natural beauty of the place and the relationship between the tribal people and the animals on them. It is a heart-warming documentary which is thematically analyzed in this research paper which tries to find out the reason behind the formation of familial relationship between the couple and the elephant.

Keywords : Elephant, Documentary, Raghu, Boman, Bailey, Relationship, Couple

Introduction :

A film based on a circle ie news or true incident is called documentary. Documentary film making in India began in 1888. A short film of wrestlers Pundalik Dada and Krishna Navi was directed by Harishchandra Sakharam Bhatwadekar in 1888 at the Hanging Gardens of Bombay. This film was the first recorded documentary in India. And then in the 1930s, DG Tendulkar, a filmmaker who studied cinematography in Moscow and Germany, brought the latest concepts of documentary film to India and started the documentary film movement in India.

The importance of documentary can be traced to the fact that the Government of India formed the Films Division in April 1948 and described the Films Division as "the official organ of the Government of India for the production and distribution of information films and newspapers". Screening of documentaries of the Films Division before feature films was made mandatory in all cinema halls in India and then documentaries were shown in India before feature films.

In 1978, Vinod Chopra directed a documentary about Bombay street children called An Encounter with Face, which went to Hollywood and was nominated for an Oscar. The documentary won nine out of 12 awards at the Oberhausen Film Festival, and also won top-level awards at festivals in Milan, Leipzig and Finland, and won the Golden Peacock Award at the International Film Festival of India.

As time progressed, mass communication studies started in India and after that the liberalization of TV channels started, which changed the format of showing documentaries and various types of documentary competitions were organized and in today's time, documentaries have become popular is released on ott platform.

Objectives :

- To analyses the relationship between people and animals living in the forest.
- To analyses the history of documentary in Indian cinema.
- To understanding the objective of Documentary Director.

Research Methodology :

A film can be analyzed in many ways, whose various methods are available in today's time, yet it is a challenging task for the researcher to choose a good method. This research paper used the thematic analytic research method, a method for analyzing qualitative data that involves reading through a set of data and looking for patterns in the meaning of the data to find themes. It is an active process of reflexivity in which the subjective experience of the researcher is central to understanding the data. Subjective experience plays an important role in finding meaning with in data. This method tries to understand the purpose of the director .

Unit of analysis and codes

The couple character as Boman and Bailey and the elephant character as Raghu and Ammukutty, codes and themes related to the Family Relationship characteristics.

1. Body Language: Confident/Sensitive
2. Dress: Simple / Vintage
3. Character: Impressive/Emotional
4. Temperament: Patience / Sad
5. Attitude towards life: Optimistic/Pessimistic

Body Language:

As the documentary begins, a man is seen standing in the forest who calls himself the king of the forest and calls every living being in the forest a member of his family. And shown as a person who believes in God. There is also a woman who lives with Boman and has the same nature as Boman. Both of them belong to the Kattunayakan tribe. People of this tribe often live in forests. Are. Whose husband is killed by a tiger, together they take care of Raghu, an orphaned baby elephant given by the forest department, and as Raghu grows up, he becomes a part of the family and How Raghu will eat, how he is feeling, Boman and Bailey understand Raghu's good upbringing, forest department hands over another elephant's orphaned baby Ammu to this couple, Raghu and Ammu play together, two orphaned elephants A relationship of trust, love and belonging is formed between the couple who bring up the children. And this tribe marries in the forest by the collective methods of the community, in which Raghu and Jammu are also present, one day again when Raghu grows up, the forest department takes Raghu and the house becomes full of music like a family member. Have left and gone and in the end this family takes care of Ammu and along with them the children living in the forest also start taking care of the elephants. This documentary depicts the nature of an elephant that they are sensitive, understanding and selflessly loving creatures.

Dress-:

In the beginning, Bimal and Bailey are shown dressed according to the old or tribal costumes in almost all the scenes which prove that they are very sensitive and loyal to the forest. And the jungle is their life. As the film progresses, their bond grows stronger and they become a family. Beli and Bimal are shown getting married in the forest dressed in new clothes and elephants are also dressed with flower garlands. This unbreakable relationship of care and affection is shown to be ending.

Character- :

All the characters have their own role in the documentary. All the characters are sensitive and calm. Where Bimal goes to bathe the elephant, Belly feeds them and they all support each other. There is no competition between them. Together they nurture the children of both elephants and also explain the importance of nature's role in people's lives.

Temperament:-

They are shown to be very patient and calm as the documentary begins. He is living life in the jungle and he considers elephants as his God because he thinks that he is getting food because of elephants. When he returns, the character's vision disappears as he is separated from a member of his family. After this, in the end, he gives a message to the children of the forest to take care of the wildlife.

Approach towards life:-

Bomman and Bela's approach towards life is very simple. They believe that this forest is their life and the people living here are their family members. Bela and Bomman have faced many challenges in their life. Lost her husband and son, there is no one for Bomman either. Both of them are calm and sensitive, they are living in a small house in the forest, and they have no greed for life, nature is their jewel, in which they live is satisfied.

Conclusion:-

This documentary gives us many messages that if we want to protect the forests and the animals living in them, then we also have to adopt the sensitivity of the people living in the forests. And in today's era of technology, we also have to think about the life of wildlife, take care of the civilization and development of the people living there. In this documentary the director has shown these two words "love and trust" very well and we all are living life on the basis of love and trust. The example of a peaceful life can be given to the whole world. The director has shown the life of the jungle by studying it very deeply and using the cinematography of the camera very skillfully. Bimal does not need anyone's voice, he himself tells about the life of the forest in the documentary. In this documentary, there is no need of words in many places, the scenes can also be understood by emotions. Will play an important role in directors and people associated with the field of film research

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